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DEMONSTRATION OF INTRADAY MARKET COUPLING IMPLICIT AUCTION BETWEEN EU AND NON-EU COUNTRIES

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Abstract — This paper presents the results of a demonstration of intraday market coupling between different market areas using an auction mechanism. The target model of internal European electricity market for Intraday trading foresees implicit allocations of cross-border capacities, which means that electricity and capacity are traded simultaneously. Intraday auctions (IDAs) will serve as complement to the continuous Single Intra-Day Coupling (SIDC). They will offer added value to existing practice as a new intraday product that fills up periods between day-ahead auctions and beginning of continuous trade, determines the cross-zonal capacity price and enables optimal market participants' portfolio. The estimated go live of IDA in internal European market is expected during 2024.

In this paper, described are the business process, products, relations between the involved entities, intraday market coupling benefits as well as the results of the experiment. The geographic area of the experiment covered Hungary (HUPX) and Serbia (SEEPEX), with Montenegro (BELEN) which played a role of an import-export zone. Like in Day-Ahead Market (DAM) auctions, the EUPHEMIA algorithm was used to solve the pricing problem as requested by the Regulation (ACER decision on Algorithm methodology). Two products were tested: 15 min MTU covering 12h of the current day, and 60 min MTU covering 24h of the following day. Both un-congested and congested test-cases were performed. The results clearly demonstrate that electricity market coupling between EU and Non-EU countries brings benefits to both sides. The paper also shows that small-size markets with lower intraday liquidity, or the markets that do not find business interest to implement full intraday market coupling using auction mechanism, still can access a liquid market that is coupled to integrated Pan-EU market.

Key words — Cross Zonal Capacity, EUPHEMIA algorithm, Implicit Allocation, Import/Export Zone, Intraday Auction, SIDC

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1 INTRODUCTION

In accordance with the ACER Decision No. 01_2019 24th of January 2019 [1], three mandatory IDAs shall be performed as implicit auctions with hourly/half-hourly/quarter hourly/simple block products. Intraday auctions (IDAs) will serve as complement to the continuous Single Intra-Day Coupling (SIDC) [2]. The estimated go live of IDA is expected in 2024. A few regional IDAs have been already implemented on certain markets (EPEX, SEMO-Nord Pool, hEnEx etc). However, South-Eastern Europe (SEE) is still facing substantial barriers to improve the current situation and facilitate the coupling of SEE electricity markets not only between themselves, but also within other EU market areas. For this reasons, TRINITY project was planned to address these challenges and to propose solutions and tools to augment cooperation and coordination among the transmission system and market operators of SEE in order to support the integration of the electricity markets in the region, whilst promoting higher penetration of clean energies [3].

1.1 TRINITY Project - Overview

The project rationale

TRINITY (**TR**ansmission system enhancement of reg**Io**Nal borders by means of **Intell**igen**T** market technolog**Y**) is the project which main goal is to enhance cooperation and coordination among the Transmission System Operators of South-Eastern Europe in order to support the integration of the electricity markets in the region, whilst promoting higher penetration of clean energies [3].

TRINITY addresses the EU’s Research Horizon Framework 2020 Program within the call Building a low-carbon, climate resilient future: secure, clean and efficient energy (“LC-SC3-ES-2-2019: Solutions for increased regional cross-border cooperation in the transmission grid”. TRINITY’s team is composed of 19 partners from 11 countries. The three main drivers of the project objectives: **Market integration, TSOs coordination and RES promotion** – are directly covered by three of the TRINITY products, that will interact together thanks to the fourth project result, the T-COORDINATION PLATFORM, as shown in Figure 1 a).

Figure 1: a) TRINITY products interaction; b) T-MARKET Coupling Framework platform; c) Geographical scope of the experiment

T-MARKET Coupling Framework

TRINITY is aimed to enhance cross-border cooperation and ensure electricity market integration at the regional level as an important and necessary step in the process of integration of the SEE countries into a common internal European electricity market.

The T-Market Coupling platform consists of four separate modules covering different areas: intra-day electricity trade, trade of a common regional capacity reserve, bilateral trading and Guarantees of Origins trading, see Figure 1 b). These modules (except bilateral trading) are based on a market auction method used in already developed markets in Western and Central Europe and that will be adapted by SEEPEX and EPEX to SEE. The partners participating in the development of each module are listed in the diagram.

These tools can be used both in the region and between the EU and non-EU countries, as a transitional solution for the full transposition of all European regulations and their binding implementation and accession to the European common market initiative.

The focus in this paper will be on the Intraday Market Coupling Auction (ID MCA) Tool.

Geographical scope of the experiment

Geographical scope of the experiment encompasses Hungary and Serbia, with Montenegro. The goal was to demonstrate the intraday coupling using auction mechanism between two PXs: HUPX and SEEPEX, with an export/import zone - MEPX, as displayed in Figure 1 c).

ID MCA Tool

The Market Coupling Tool’s process diagram is presented in Figure 2. TSOs (in this demonstration it was Serbian TSO – EMS) submits cross zonal capacity (CZC) files containing Available Transfer Capacities (ATC) for both borders in both directions, i.e. for Serbian-Hungarian border but also for the border between Serbia and Montenegro, to the Market Coupling Operator (EPEX spot).

Figure 2 Market Coupling Tool process diagram

The reason for this is because Hungarian TSO (MAVIR) was not part of the Project Consortium. Market participants, on the other side, submit the order books containing their offers and bids to the EPEX spot Trading System. T-RES platform was one of the Market Participants taking an active part in the demonstration. Providing all the capacity files and order books are successfully received at EPEX spot, at the specified time which is for the first intraday auction 4 PM (for 60 min MTU products), and for the second intraday auction 10 AM (for 15 min MTU products), the auction is executed. Market Coupling Operator passes the aggregated order books and CZC files to the algorithm and receives the results back from the algorithm. All the results, for the coupled markets and for each market participant, altogether with Operation Market Messages, are sent to SEEPEX SFTP server. The results and messages are added to a Database and are published on the dedicated T-Market Website. The dedicated website was developed by SEEPEX and it makes visible all results obtained during the demonstration. From the SFTP server, the corresponding results are also forwarded to each Market Participant. All these steps are a part of normal pre-coupling, coupling and post coupling procedures that can usually be seen in coupled auctions in Europe and other regions.

2 INNOVATIONS BROUGHT BY THE INTRADAY MARKET COUPLING TOOL

Maintaining a stable price signal

Green transition and future changes of the power system have the potential to affect how and when electricity is traded. Renewable electricity growth is accelerating faster than ever, increasing the volume of energy being supplied by variable renewable generation technologies, the output of which is relatively uncertain at the day-ahead stage **Error! Reference source not found.**[6]. This implies that cross-zonal intraday trade is important to effectively optimise the international power system [7]. Under the current challenging circumstances implementation of new market mechanisms is the key in reinforcing the Intraday reference price, optimising the short-term market and facilitating the energy transition.

TRINITY Intraday Market Coupling Auction (IDMCA) Module of T-MARKET COUPLING FRAMEWORK will enable the cross-border auctioning of energy in the intraday timeframe bringing an additional opportunity to the existing market mechanisms, reflecting the importance of intraday re-optimisation of cross-zonal flows.

IDAs increase the depth and liquidity of intraday markets providing an opportunity to traders to offer their full flexibility even without maintaining a 24-hour trading team. Additionally implementing cross-border intraday auctions enables the pricing of cross-zonal capacities entailing the more effective use of cross-zonal capacities in line with the first-come-first-serve approach.

The design and development phase of the new TRINITY cross-border intraday auction has been finalised in a harmonised manner with the Pan-European IDA Project to fit the proposed solution to the European Target Model.

Testing the shortest lead time

The proposed solution delivers two separate intraday auctions (IDAs) for the same delivery day (day D):

The first IDA will be performed on day D-1 at 16:00 with hourly and block products, while the second IDA on the consecutive day (day D) at 10:00 with finer granularity, anticipating the fact that 2024 Pan-EU IDAs will see 15 minutes MTU (Market Time Unit) implemented in all trading and capacity allocation assets in all compatible market areas and on all relevant borders. The new quarter hourly products allow market participants to adjust their market position when trading occurs closer to delivery.

Presenting a technical solution for the SEE region

This module will present a technical solution of market coupling between EU and non-EU (Energy Community) countries which is entirely compatible with the already existing, widely-used market coupling platforms taken into consideration the unique features of local markets to make the idea feasible.

Why IDA? - Background

The demonstration will take place between Serbia, Hungary with the inclusion of Montenegro. SEEPEX [8] operates the organized electricity market in Serbia, with standardized electricity products and delivery within a time frame of day-ahead with the goal to offer these electricity products for trading in Serbia and in the SEE region, where appropriate. Currently intraday trading is not available at SEEPEX, IDAs would open a new market segment to gravitate more market participants towards to the organised market.

HUPX [9] is truly engaged towards to the further development of electricity markets and as a NEMO obliged to execute the SIDC in Hungary. TRINITY brings a great opportunity to co-operate other PXs outside of EU, test challenging market scenarios with the aim of potential extensions of the IDA project.

EPEX SPOT operates a wide range of Intraday auctions, either its own name or on behalf of other NEMOs, completing the trading value chain. Deployment of IDAs in TRINITY can serve as a base to provide more tailored services aligned to the new trading patterns of SEE region.

Challenges

Although auction-based electricity trading has well-established base considering the existing European markets to develop a feasible solution for all participants inconsistencies had to be investigated and tackled by the partners:

- Harmonisation of trading portfolios
- number of traders to be set (preparation of input files)
- different range of products (introduction of 15 min blocks)
- different market specification (exclusion of negative prices)

Although the regulatory framework of the EU integration of Energy Community Members is out of the scope, TRINITY addresses a roadmap for the SEE region for market coupling representing a logic step towards the Pan-European electricity market integration including all Energy Community members.

Engaging small markets with lower liquidity

One of the main innovations brought up by this platform is implementation of Export/Import zone (EIZ). EIZ represents small markets (countries), markets with lower intraday liquidity, markets that do not find business interest to implement full intraday market coupling using auction mechanism. This will enable such markets to access liquid market that is coupled to integrated Pan-EU market. The market participants from such markets will have an opportunity to adjust their position through this product.

Advancements to existing coupling processes

An innovative technical setup will be tested in this module. The envisaged technical solution is simplified and the Cross zonal Capacity (using ATC) submission from TSOs to the central coupling assets will be streamlined without the need of an intermediate Power Exchange (PX) system. Indeed, TSO (EMS in the case of HU-RS IDA) will have the technical possibility to submit the capacity directly to central coupling assets. This simplified process reduces the implementation and operational costs, and HU-RS IDAs project Parties believe this option could be implemented in the Pan-EU IDAs project.

The capacity allocation between Hungary (CACM EU Member State) and Serbia (non-CACM and non-EU country) will be validated during the initiative thanks to national regulatory framework adaptation, a robust contractual framework amongst power Exchanges and TSOs, as well as a generic technical solution.

3 INTRADAY MARKET COUPLING EXPERIMENT DESCRIPTION

In this section, the main features of the experiment, such as performed tests, involved actors, used assets and systems, as well as a description of the experiment are presented.

Tests to be performed:

- Market participants connectivity check
- CZC files creation using SCC/T-SENTINEL tool for optimal cross-border capacity calculation (for both 15 min MTU and 60 min MTU)
- CZC files submission using webservice and CZC file format check
- Bid files submission with format check
- Upload input data in market coupling tool (both manually and using EXCEL)
- Testing pre-coupling procedures and coupling tests by Market Operator
- Sending pre-coupling results to HUPX
- Uploading market results to SEEPEX's SFTP
- Retrieving the results by the market participants
- Generating/Sending/Receiving all OMMs (Operating Market Message)
- Publishing market results to the dedicated Trinity Webpage

Actors involved in the experiment: EPEX Spot, HUPX, BELEN, EMS, CGES, SEEPEX

Assets and systems used in the experiment:

At EPEX Spot side, the system for this experiment contained:

- ETS (Energy Trading System) that allows market participants to connect, submit their bids/offers, review the existing bids/offers, and retrieve the results
- MCO (Market Coupling Operator) system that performs coupling
- LISE that gathers market results and send them to SEEPEX SFTP
- SFTP at SEEPEX that is a hub for sending/receiving all data and results required for ID MCA
- MySQL Database in which all the results are stored

At SEEPEX side:

- Dedicated website (built on “WordPress” platform) where the selected results are displayed
- SEEPEX SFTP server to gather and communicate data with EPEX SPOT, EMS and market participants

At the market participants’ side:

- The only requirement for this experiment is that ETS client is installed and properly configured with a stable internet connection speed.

Description of the experiment:

- IDA auctions in two consecutive days:
 - On day D-1 at 16:00: Intraday auction 60 min MTU, delivery period on day D 00-24h
 - On Day D at 10:00, Intraday auction 15 min MTU, delivery period for the same day 12-24h
- Auctions: weekly, for 15 weeks (each week one 60 min auction and one 15-minute auction)
- Products: linear orders + regular blocks + smart blocks
- Coupling between Hungary and Serbia, with Montenegro being an import/export area connected to Serbia
- EMS (Serbian TSO) sends CZCs for all borders: HU-RS and ME-RS
- T-RES platform provides bids
- Market/auction status messages will be sent to T- Coordination platform and to T-Market Web site

Two test cases are tested: scenario with no congestion on Hungary-Serbia border; and scenario with congestion on this border.

4 INTRADAY MARKET COUPLING EXPERIMENT RESULTS

The experiment took place within 15 consecutive weeks in between 06. September 2022 and 14. December 2022. In the first ten weeks, the tests were performed with realistic Net Transfer Capacity (NTC) on the interconnecting line between Hungary and Serbia. With these capacities, no congestion was identified in scheduled power flows (in both directions) between Hungary and Serbia, and the prices in all market areas were the same, Figure 3 a) and Figure 3b). On contrary, in last five tests, a congestion on the mentioned line and all consequences and impacts that it could cause on market coupling process, were tested (Figure 3 c) and Figure 3 d)).

In the rest of this Section, two randomly selected tests (one in non-congested conditions, and another one in the simulated congestion on the Serbia-Hungary border) are analysed. Section 4.1 describes the non-congested test that was run on 04. October (IDA1) and on 05. October (IDA2). In the second test, presented in Section 4.2, a congestion on the Serbia-Hungary border was simulated. This test was run on 25.11.2022 (IDA1) and on 25.11.2022 (IDA2).

Figure 3: a) Market Clearing Price for IDA1 (60 min MTU) on 04.10.2022, non-congestion case; b) Market Clearing Price for IDA2 (15 min MTU) on 05.10.2022, non-congestion case; c) Market Clearing Price for IDA1 (60 min MTU) on 25.11.2022, congested case; d) Market Clearing Price for IDA2 (15 min MTU) on 25.11.2022, congested case

4.1 No congestion on the border Hungary – Serbia

TEST 1: IDA1 (60 min MTU) Market Coupling Results for 04. October 2022.

The demonstration test described here was run on 04.10.2022. This test was based on the original auctions data in Hungary and Serbia, held on 29.09.2022. The results of the test are displayed in Figure 4.

Figure 4 Results of IDA1 (60 min MTU) on 04.10.2022, non-congestion case

Figure 3 a) discloses the same Market Clearing Price (MCP) in all three market areas: Hungary, Montenegro and Serbia. The reason for this is because the Available Transfer Capacity (ATC) values are higher than the cross-border flows (see Figure 4 a) and b)), and so no congestion occurs in all borders.

The total traded volume is defined as a sum of buy and sell volumes, and it is represented as the height of each bar in Figure 4 c), d) and e) for Hungary, Montenegro and Serbia, respectively. In the figures, buy volume is marked blue (lower part of bars) whilst the sell volume (upper part of bars) is marked green.

For each country, net position is calculated as a difference between Export volume and Import Volume. These quantities are visualised in Figure 4 f), g) and h). Note that all results are available on the dedicated Trinity website*.

TEST 2: IDA2 (15 min MTU) Market Coupling Results for 05. October 2022, no congestion

The demonstration test for IDA2 market coupling described in this document was made on 05.06.2022. The same experiment arrangement as for IDA1 applies also to IDA2. The main difference is that in IDA2, the Market Time Unit is 15 min. As explained before, IDA2 is designed to cover delivery period of 12 hours in 15-minute resolution starting from hour 13 and ending with hour 24 of the same day when the auction is made. In this test, there was no congestion on the Hungary-Serbia border. Summarized market results, along with available network capacities for this specific pre-demonstration test are given in Figure 3 b) and Figure 5.

Figure 5 Results of IDA1 (60 min MTU) on 04.10.2022, non-congestion case

* <https://www.trinity-t-market-coupling-framework.com>

In Figure 3 b), the Market Clearing Price (MCP) for all three market areas is presented. Again, the MCPs are the same in all three areas since there is no congestion. Other results (total traded volume, export and import volumes, as well as net position) are shown in Figure 5 a) – h).

4.2 Simulation of congestion on the border Hungary - Serbia

TEST 3: IDA1 (60 min MTU) Market Coupling Results for 25. November 2022.

The demonstration test described here was originally run on 22.11.2022. with no congestion on the Hungary-Serbian border, and re-run on 25.11.2022. with limited ATC to simulate congestion on the border. Coupling tests with simulated congestion were made in three steps:

- 1) Non-congested coupling auction was simulated first. Power flows on the HU-RS border were recorded.
- 2) Power flows recorded in Step 1 were reduced by 10% and these values are set as actual CZC/ATC on Hungary-Serbia border. ATC on Serbia-Montenegro border remained intact (no congestion on this border).
- 3) The coupling process was repeated with the reduced values of CZC on HU-RS border.

The results of the IDA1 test with simulated congestion on the Hungary-Serbia border are shown in Figure 3 c) and Figure 6.

Market Clearing Prices for Hungary, Montenegro and Serbia are shown in Figure 3 c). On contrary to the non-congested case, now the MCPs in Hungarian market area differ from the ones in Serbian market area. Prices in Montenegrin and Serbian market area are the same, since the ATCs are set much higher than the power flows between the two countries.

Figure 6 Results of IDA1 (60 min MTU) on 25.11.2022, congested case

ATCs and power flows between Montenegro and Serbia are graphically represented in Figure 6 a). There is no congestion on this border since the ATCs are greater than power flows for all times. Contrary, the flows between Hungary and Serbia are limited by the available transfer capacities, hence the congestion occurs, as displayed in Figure 6 b).

TEST 4: IDA2 (15 min MTU) Market Coupling Results for 25. November 2022.

The demonstration test for IDA2 market coupling described here was originally made on 23.11.2022. without a congestion and then re-run on 25.11.2022. with reduced ATC to simulate congestion on Hungary-Serbia border. The test design was the same as for IDA1: power flows are calculated in a non-congested case, the obtained values are reduced for 10% and then applied as CZC.

The results of the IDA2 test with simulated congestion on the Hungary-Serbia border are shown in Figure 3 d) and Figure 7.

Due to the imposed congestion, there was a price difference between Hungarian and Serbian market areas: whenever power flows reach the CZC limits, prices differ from each other, and vice versa, when the power flow is less than the CZC, prices converge, as shown in Figure 3 d).

Other results (total traded volume, export and import volumes, as well as net position) are shown in Figure 7 a) – h).

Figure 7 Results of IDA2 (15 min MTU) on 25.11.2022, congested case

5 CONCLUSIONS

This paper describes new cross-border intraday auctions, developed and demonstrated between an EU and a non-EU country as a part of activities within TRINITY project. All design features used in the demonstration reflect the requirements set in the EU-wide IDA project in accordance with the principles set in the CACM. Furthermore, this solution brought quite a few advancements compared to the European intraday market coupling development. Intraday market coupling based on the implicit auction mechanism and standardized products will be part of the Single Intraday Market Coupling that will be obliged for EU countries from 2024 and complement to the existing continuous trading (XBID).

This demonstration and the presented results show that all requirements and preconditions needed for the market coupling based on implicit auction between EU and non-EU countries have been met. From the technical point of view, it was demonstrated that it is feasible to couple EU and non-EU markets that have an operational NEMO, without any risks. However, the main obstacle to the integration of non-EU markets into the internal EU market is the transposition of adequate EU regulations into national legislation.

Considering the obtained results, the demonstration showed that current cross-zonal capacity is large enough to enable additional electricity flows, price convergence and establishment of a single regional marginal price between the market areas included in this simulation. This is an excellent indicator that there is sufficient capacity for investment and integration of renewable sources to achieve a successful energy transition and green agenda.

6 REFERENCES

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7 APPENDIX

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